

Engineering project - ESTACA

Evaluation of unsteady aerodynamic regimes and their influence on the aerodynamic performance of a Formula Student front wing

Phase 2 tracking sheet

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Jan. 07, 2025

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Magenta = new parts

Acronyms

CFD: Computational Fluid Dynamics

GE: Ground Effect

TE: Trailing Edge

BOI: Body Of Influence

UDF: User Defined Function

Variables and Parameters

Non dimensional

C_L : Lift coefficient (–)

C_D : Drag coefficient (–)

Displacements

$z(t)$: Heave (m)

$\alpha(t)$: Pitch angle (rad)

Other

k : Turbulent Kinetic Energy

1. Objectives

Extract from the draft proposal:

Goal: Simulate two moving flaps to observe unsteady flow response.

2.1 Analyse a configuration with one moving flap

2.2 Analyse a configuration with one fixed flap and one moving flap to assess interaction effects.

2.3 Extend to one fixed flap and two moving flaps to capture coupled aerodynamic behaviour.

2. Numerical Methodology

2.1 Computational Tool and Solver Setup

The simulations were performed using ANSYS Fluent 2025 R2 that allows the modeling of unsteady, moving-boundary problems through its *Dynamic Mesh* capability. The study was conducted in transient mode to capture the time-dependent aerodynamic effects induced by the flap motion.

The $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model was selected due to its ability to accurately resolve near-wall flow gradients while maintaining robustness in separated and recirculating regions.

The physical time step was set to $\Delta t = 0.005$ s, with a maximum of 30 iterations per time step to achieve local convergence. The total simulated duration was 1 second, corresponding to 200-time steps of 0.005 s each. The prescribed flap motion occurred over the first 0.4 seconds, after which the flow was allowed to evolve freely for an additional 0.6 seconds to observe the stabilization of the wake.

Each simulation is run with a velocity inlet of 20 m/s with a moving floor to reproduce the ground effect.

2.2 Geometry and Mesh

The geometry used in this study was initially designed in SolidWorks as a two-dimensional model. The model was then exported in IGES format and imported into ANSYS.

Once imported, a clean-up and domain construction process was carried out in ANSYS SpaceClaim to ensure a suitable computational setup for dynamic simulations.

The first step consisted of creating the flow envelope, defining the boundaries of the fluid region. This envelope was sized to provide sufficient clearance upstream, downstream, and above the geometry to minimize boundary interference effects.

Moreover, the Body of Influence (BOI) was created around the flaps to locally refine the mesh and improve accuracy near the walls, where strong velocity gradients and flow separation occur.

This refinement ensures that the computational cells are smaller and more regular in the regions where aerodynamic effects are most significant.

Additionally, the BOI allows the moving mesh to be applied only to the localized zone around the flaps, rather than to the entire flow domain.

This approach reduces computational cost and prevents unnecessary deformation of the outer envelope, ensuring that only the relevant part of the mesh is dynamically updated during flap motion.

Following domain construction, named selections were assigned to each boundary zone to facilitate setup in Fluent:

- Inlet
- Outlet
- Floor
- Wall
- Flaps
- Interface between moving and static domain

Near-wall refinement was achieved through multiple inflation layers, ensuring that the y^+ values stay around 1.

2.3 Dynamic Mesh and UDF Implementation

To accurately model the rotation of the flaps during the transient simulation, the Dynamic Mesh feature of ANSYS Fluent was combined with a User-Defined Function (UDF) written in C language.

This approach enabled precise control over the flap motion while allowing the mesh to deform smoothly around the moving regions.

```
#include "udf.h"
/* Flap F1 */
#define X_PIVOT_F1 (-0.382)
#define Y_PIVOT_F1 (0.01002)
#define FINAL_ANGLE_F1 (0.349) /* +20° */
#define FINAL_TIME_F1 (0.4)

/* Flap F2 */
#define X_PIVOT_F2 (-0.45472)
#define Y_PIVOT_F2 (0.05348)
#define FINAL_ANGLE_F2 (0.349) /* +20° */
#define FINAL_TIME_F2 (0.4)

/* FLAP 1 */
DEFINE_CG_MOTION(flap_F1_ramp, dt, vel, omega, time, dtime)
{
    real angle_now, angle_prev;
    vel[0]=0.0; vel[1]=0.0;
    DT_CG(dt)[0]=X_PIVOT_F1;
    DT_CG(dt)[1]=Y_PIVOT_F1;

    angle_now = (time<=FINAL_TIME_F1) ? FINAL_ANGLE_F1*(time/FINAL_TIME_F1) : FINAL_ANGLE_F1;
    angle_prev = ((time-dtime)<=FINAL_TIME_F1) ? FINAL_ANGLE_F1*((time-dtime)/FINAL_TIME_F1) : FINAL_ANGLE_F1;

    omega[0]=0.0; omega[1]=0.0;
    omega[2]=(dtime>0.0)?(angle_now-angle_prev)/dtime:0.0;
}

/* FLAP 2 */
DEFINE_CG_MOTION(flap_F2_ramp, dt, vel, omega, time, dtime)
{
    real angle_now, angle_prev;
    vel[0]=0.0; vel[1]=0.0;
    DT_CG(dt)[0]=X_PIVOT_F2;
    DT_CG(dt)[1]=Y_PIVOT_F2;

    angle_now = (time<=FINAL_TIME_F2) ? FINAL_ANGLE_F2*(time/FINAL_TIME_F2) : FINAL_ANGLE_F2;
    angle_prev = ((time-dtime)<=FINAL_TIME_F2) ? FINAL_ANGLE_F2*((time-dtime)/FINAL_TIME_F2) : FINAL_ANGLE_F2;

    omega[0]=0.0; omega[1]=0.0;
    omega[2]=(dtime>0.0)?(angle_now-angle_prev)/dtime:0.0;
}
```


In this study, the Dynamic Mesh model was configured using two main methods: smoothing and remeshing.

Smoothing:

The smoothing method allows the mesh to deform gradually as the flap moves, ensuring that cell shapes remain acceptable without changing the overall mesh connectivity.

It redistributes the position of internal nodes according to the motion of the boundaries, maintaining a smooth transition between the moving and stationary zones.

This method is well-suited for moderate deformations, such as the flap rotation in this study, as it preserves mesh quality efficiently without requiring frequent remeshing.

Remeshing:

When the local deformation exceeded the limits that smoothing could handle, local remeshing was automatically triggered.

This ensured that any excessively skewed or stretched elements were replaced with new, high-quality cells. This avoids Negative Volume cell that we can have with only Smoothing.

2.4 Definition of the centre of rotation of the wing

C3.11.6 Rear Wing Adjuster System

The “Rear Wing Adjuster System” is defined as follows:

- a. “RW Flap” is constructed solely from **Rear Wing Profiles** and must:
 - i. exclude all the forwardmost volume.
 - ii. exclude all remaining volumes outboard of $Y = 535$.
 - iii. include all remaining volumes inboard of $Y = 530$.
 - iv. include any fitted **Gurney** and any parts of **Rear Wing Auxiliary Components** that are attached to any included volumes.
- b. Adjustment of **RW Flap** is about a fixed axis of rotation which must:
 - i. be aligned with a Y-Axis.
 - ii. lie within **RV-RW-PROFILES**.
 - iii. at $Y = 50$, lie between the rearmost point and the mid-point of **RW Flap**, measured in the X-direction.
 - iv. between $Y = 50$ and inboard of $Y = 535$, when viewed from below, be fully obscured by **RW Flap**.

The centre of rotation should be between the rearmost point (the TE) and the mid point (mid chord point) of the RW Flap

3. Getting Started with the Moving Mesh

3.1 Single Moving Flap without Ground Effect

The first simulation was carried out on a simple S1223 flap, with the main objective of understanding the fundamental behaviour of the Moving Mesh method.

The initial setup served as a baseline to explore how Fluent manages mesh deformation around moving surface.

The flap was prescribed to rotate by -20° over 0.4 seconds.

This first configuration confirmed that the UDF correctly controlled the flap rotation, and the mesh could adapt dynamically, but the centre of rotation was in (0,0)

It provided a solid foundation for extending the study to more complex cases.

3.2 One Fixed flap and one Moving flap without Ground effect

The second simulation introduced a more complex configuration composed of two flaps in series, a fixed S6063 and a S1223 flap :

The main objective of this simulation was to understand how to correctly manage the rotation centre within the UDF code, ensuring that the flap rotated precisely around its leading edge.

3.3 One Fixed flap and two Moving flaps with Ground effect

The final simulation aimed to implement the complete methodology developed in the previous cases and to move closer to a more realistic aerodynamic configuration. This setup included one fixed flap and two independently moving flaps, each controlled by its own UDF.

This approach allowed the definition of two distinct pivot points, ensuring that each flap rotated accurately around its respective leading edge.

However, during the simulation, some issues related to mesh deformation were observed.

In certain regions, the dynamic mesh stretched excessively, particularly near the hinge areas. This behaviour indicates that the current smoothing and remeshing parameters need to be adjusted to improve mesh quality and prevent over-stretching.

Initial Mesh

Mesh after the simulation

Finally, post-processing was attempted to visualize the transient results through animations and contours plots.

Unfortunately, the generated outputs were not fully exploitable due to insufficient image resolution and incompatible video formats.

Overall, this final simulation successfully validated the UDF implementation for multiple moving bodies but highlighted the need for further optimization of dynamic mesh parameters and enhanced post-processing for detailed aerodynamic analysis.

With the improved mesh, we had difficulties making the transient simulation. But after modifying some parameters, we finally got it.

We can see that the mesh after simulation is better than with our previous settings, but we can still improve it by changing settings.

Now we must change the UDF, because the F1 has a negative angle after simulation. That's because we changed and optimized the angles of attack on every flap, after our first test on dynamic mesh.

The new angles of attacks are:

f1 : 10.55 °

f2 : 32.55°

That means that after the DRS simulation of 1 second the flaps should be:

f1 : 0 °

f2 : 12.55°

4. Python Automatization

4.1 Our needs

This section is about writing a Python program that will automate all the results so that we won't have to do it by hand. It may take some time to implement and to code, but it will be worth it in the near future.

This program is being developed in VSCode with Python because it is the language Ansys understands and can manipulate easily.

We will have to make all the simulations as always until the initialization. By then, we will have to exit Fluent and run the .py. The program will open in the background Fluent and will do the simulation by itself. At each iteration, it will extract the residuals and make a graphic as .png for us. It will also make some other graphics (Cl & Cd vs angle1 and angle2).

We will also get an animation in the MP4 format, which will be easily watched and analysed.

4.2 Python code explanation

```
1 import os
2 import sys
3 from pathlib import Path
4 import subprocess
5 import logging
6 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
7 import pandas as pd
8 from ansys.fluent.core import launch_fluent
```

The first part of the code is to imports all necessary Python modules:

- os, sys, and Path — file and path management
- subprocess — for running external programs (e.g. ffmpeg)
- logging — structured console output
- matplotlib and pandas — for plotting and saving simulation data
- ansys.fluent.core — Fluent Python API for automation

```
# ----- CONFIG -----
project_dir = Path("") # <-- METTRE ICI le dossier du projet
cas_file = project_dir / "Dynamic_mesh.cas"
dat_file = project_dir / "Dynamic_mesh.dat"
udf_path = project_dir / "motion UDF.c"
output_dir = project_dir / "output_frames"
csv_file = project_dir / "forces_residuals.csv"
mp4_file = project_dir / "DRS_animation.mp4"
graph_file = project_dir / "Cl_Cd_DRS_angles_residuals.png"
```


The next steps are to get and export all our needed information from Fluent in our documents. We want to keep our project path clean, so that it will be easily accessible.

```
# Fluent / runtime
fluent_version = "2025R2"
solver_mode = "2d"
num_cores = 4          # 4 ou 2 dépendant de votre capacité de calcul

# Simulation time settings
t_end = 1
dt = 0.005

# DRS angles (deg)
DRS1_init = 24.0
DRS1_final = 4.0
DRS2_init = 13.0
DRS2_final = 0.0
t_start = 0.0
t_open = 0.4

# Noms (adapter aux objets dans votre modèle/SpaceClaim / Fluent)
UDF_NAME = "drs_two_volets" # nom de la fonction UDF après compilation
FORCES_MONITOR_NAME = "Forces_DRS"
RESIDUALS_MONITOR_NAME = "Residuals"
FORCE_SURFACES = ["FW F2", "FW F3"] # surfaces/coques utilisées pour les coefficients

# Logging
logging.basicConfig(level=logging.INFO, format="%(asctime)s - %(levelname)s - %(message)s")
```

For the program to work with Ansys Fluent, we have to specify all our data that we are using in the simulations. Right now, it has names and numbers that aren't these that we are using; it is only an example.

```
# ----- VALIDATIONS LOCALES -----
def validate_inputs():
    if not project_dir or not project_dir.exists():
        logging.error("project_dir non renseigné ou n'existe pas. Mettez le chemin du dossier projet.")
        sys.exit(1)
    if not cas_file.exists():
        logging.error(f"Fichier .cas introuvable: {cas_file}")
        sys.exit(1)
    if not dat_file.exists():
        logging.warning(f"Fichier .dat introuvable: {dat_file} - ce n'est pas fatal si vous voulez recharger la géométrie seulement.")
    if not udf_path.exists():
        logging.warning(f"UDF introuvable: {udf_path}. Ignorer si vous n'utilisez pas d'UDF compilée.")

validate_inputs()
output_dir.mkdir(parents=True, exist_ok=True)
```

To be even more precise, we have checks on all our code, that will make it viable. If the .dat or .cas isn't recognised or not in the documents it will show us a message, so that Fluent won't do a silent crash. This can happen, because we are running Fluent in the background with this program.

In the next steps, we will launch Fluent with python.


```
# ----- LANCEMENT FLUENT -----  
try:  
    logging.info("Lancement de Fluent..")  
    fl = launch_fluent(version=fluent_version, precision="double", processor_count=num_cores, mode=solver_mode)  
except Exception as e:  
    logging.exception("Impossible de lancer Fluent. Vérifiez l'installation et la version.")  
    raise
```

Again, it will try to open. If it doesn't work, the program won't proceed in launching.

```
# Lecture cas/dat  
try:  
    logging.info("Lecture du fichier .cas")  
    fl.file.read(str(cas_file))  
    if dat_file.exists():  
        logging.info("Lecture du fichier .dat")  
        fl.file.read_data(str(dat_file))  
except Exception as e:  
    logging.exception("Erreur pendant la lecture des fichiers .cas/.dat")  
    raise  
  
# Dynamic mesh  
try:  
    logging.info("Activation Dynamic Mesh")  
    fl.dynamic_mesh.enable()  
    fl.dynamic_mesh.set_parameters(smoothing_iterations=30, remesh_frequency=1, min_cell_quality=0.25)  
except Exception:  
    logging.exception("Impossible de configurer le Dynamic Mesh. Continuer si non critique.")  
  
# Charger et charger l'UDF  
if udf_path.exists():  
    try:  
        logging.info("Compilation et chargement de l'UDF")  
        fl.udf.compile(str(udf_path))  
        fl.udf.load(UDF_NAME)  
    except Exception:  
        logging.exception("Erreur compilation/chargement UDF. Vérifiez le code UDF et le nom de la fonction.")  
else:  
    logging.info("Aucun UDF trouvé / UDF ignoré.")
```

If Fluent is launched, the .cas and .dat files will be read, and the UDF will do the same. The parameter "Dynamic mesh" will be activated.

```
# Créer / récupérer les moniteurs (création si non existants)  
# Note: si vous avez déjà créé les moniteurs dans le .cas, fl.monitors.create tentera d'en créer d'autres.  
try:  
    logging.info("Création des moniteurs (si nécessaire)")  
    # Résidus  
    try:  
        fl.monitors.residuals.create(name=RESIDUALS_MONITOR_NAME, write=True, plot=False)  
    except Exception:  
        logging.debug("Moniteur residuals déjà existant ou non-créable via l'API, continuer.")  
    # Forces (coefficients)  
    try:  
        fl.monitors.forces.create(name=FORCES_MONITOR_NAME, type="coefficients", surfaces=FORCE_SURFACES, write=True, plot=False)  
    except Exception:  
        logging.debug("Moniteur forces déjà existant ou non-créable via l'API, continuer.")  
except Exception:  
    logging.exception("Erreur lors de la configuration des moniteurs.")  
  
# Paramètres transient  
fl.solver.settings.time_step = dt  
fl.solver.settings.end_time = t_end  
fl.solver.settings.transient = True
```


The purpose of this Python code is to export easily all our data. This includes the residuals and forces, which will be done there. It will create them if necessary.

```
# ----- PREPARATION STOCKAGE -----
time_list = []
cl_list = []
cd_list = []
drs1_angle_list = []
drs2_angle_list = []
residuals_dict = {"continuity": [], "x-velocity": [], "y-velocity": [], "k": [], "omega": []}

# nombre de pas (inclusif de la dernière étape)
num_steps = int(round(t_end / dt)) + 1

# --- helpers pour récupérer les valeurs des moniteurs avec fallback ---
def safe_get_forces(mon, name):
    #Récupère lift/drag de façon robuste – la signature dépend de l'implémentation du moniteur.
    try:
        # Essayer l'API proposée dans ton script:
        if name.lower() == "lift coefficient":
            return mon.get_value("lift coefficient")
        if name.lower() == "drag coefficient":
            return mon.get_value("drag coefficient")
    except Exception:
        pass
    # tentative alternative : get_values or get_monitor_data
    try:
        vals = mon.get_values() # si disponible retourne dict/list
        # chercher 'lift'/'drag'
        if isinstance(vals, dict):
            return vals.get("lift coefficient") or vals.get("lift") or vals.get("cl")
        if isinstance(vals, (list, tuple)) and len(vals) >= 2:
            # convention : [lift, drag] – ATTENTION: spéculatif
            return vals[0]
    except Exception:
        pass
    raise RuntimeError("Impossible de récupérer la valeur de force via le moniteur.")

def safe_get_residual(mon, resid_name):
    try:
        return mon.get_value(resid_name)
    except Exception:
        # fallback: peut-être get_values avec dictionnaire
        try:
            vals = mon.get_values()
            if isinstance(vals, dict):
                return vals.get(resid_name)
        except Exception:
            pass
    # si échec, renvoyer NaN pour maintenir la longueur des listes
    logging.debug(f"Impossible de récupérer residual '{resid_name}' – mettre NaN")
    return float("nan")
```

The program will prepare the storage of all our data. It will robustly extract them, so that nothing will be lost, corrupted or problems.


```
# Récupération des objets moniteurs (si l'API le permet)
try:
    forces_monitor = fl.monitors.forces[FORCES_MONITOR_NAME]
except Exception:
    try:
        forces_monitor = fl.monitors.forces
    except Exception:
        forces_monitor = None
        logging.warning("Moniteur de forces non trouvé. Cl/Cd seront NaN.")

try:
    residuals_monitor = fl.monitors.residuals[RESIDUALS_MONITOR_NAME]
except Exception:
    try:
        residuals_monitor = fl.monitors.residuals
    except Exception:
        residuals_monitor = None
        logging.warning("Moniteur de résidus non trouvé. Résidus seront NaN.")
```

There, we will export our monitors from the simulation. We will get the residuals and the forces.

```
# ----- BOUCLE TEMPORELLE -----
logging.info(f"Démarrage de la simulation: {num_steps} pas (dt={dt}s)")

for step in range(num_steps):
    # avancée du solveur d'un pas de temps
    try:
        fl.solve_time_step()
    except Exception:
        # Certain workflows utilisent fl.solve(steps=1) ou fl.run_calculation nativement.
        logging.exception("Erreur pendant fl.solve_time_step(). Tentative d'ignorer et continuer.")
    # on peut forcer la définition du temps à step*dt pour sécurité
    t = round(step * dt, 12)
    time_list.append(t)

    # Cl / Cd avec fallback
    try:
        if forces_monitor is not None:
            # tentative d'obtenir Cl puis Cd
            try:
                cl = safe_get_forces(forces_monitor, "lift coefficient")
            except Exception:
                cl = float("nan")
            try:
                cd = safe_get_forces(forces_monitor, "drag coefficient")
            except Exception:
                cd = float("nan")
        else:
            cl, cd = float("nan"), float("nan")
    except Exception:
        logging.exception("Erreur lors de la lecture Cl/Cd")
        cl, cd = float("nan"), float("nan")

    cl_list.append(cl)
    cd_list.append(cd)
```



```
# Angles DRS (linéaire entre init et final sur [t_start, t_start+t_open])
if t < t_start:
    angle1, angle2 = DRS1_init, DRS2_init
elif t <= t_start + t_open:
    frac = (t - t_start) / t_open if t_open != 0 else 1.0
    angle1 = DRS1_init + (DRS1_final - DRS1_init) * frac
    angle2 = DRS2_init + (DRS2_final - DRS2_init) * frac
else:
    angle1, angle2 = DRS1_final, DRS2_final
drs1_angle_list.append(angle1)
drs2_angle_list.append(angle2)

# Résidus
if residuals_monitor is not None:
    residuals_dict["continuity"].append(safe_get_residual(residuals_monitor, "continuity"))
    residuals_dict["x-velocity"].append(safe_get_residual(residuals_monitor, "x-velocity"))
    residuals_dict["y-velocity"].append(safe_get_residual(residuals_monitor, "y-velocity"))
    residuals_dict["k"].append(safe_get_residual(residuals_monitor, "k"))
    residuals_dict["omega"].append(safe_get_residual(residuals_monitor, "omega"))
else:
    residuals_dict["continuity"].append(float("nan"))
    residuals_dict["x-velocity"].append(float("nan"))
    residuals_dict["y-velocity"].append(float("nan"))
    residuals_dict["k"].append(float("nan"))
    residuals_dict["omega"].append(float("nan"))

# Sauvegarde d'une image (tenter, ignorer si non disponible)
image_path = output_dir / f"frame_{step:04d}.png"
try:
    # variable et dimensions adaptables
    fl.graphics.save_image(str(image_path), width=1920, height=1080, variable="velocity magnitude")
except Exception:
    logging.debug(f"Impossible de sauvegarder l'image pour le pas {step}. Ignorer.")

# Export image Velocity Magnitude
image_path = os.path.join(output_dir, f"frame_{step:04d}.png")
try:
    fl.graphics.save_image(image_path, width=1920, height=1080, variable="velocity-magnitude", zone=domain_name, palette="Turbo", min_value=0.0, max_value=60.0)
except Exception:
    logging.debug(f"Impossible de sauvegarder l'image pour le pas {step}. Ignorer.")

# petit log intermédiaire
if step % max(1, int(0.1 * num_steps)) == 0:
    logging.info(f"Step {step+1}/{num_steps} t={t:.4f}s Cl={cl} Cd={cd} angle1={angle1:.2f}")

logging.info("Boucle temporelle terminée.")
```

For each time step:

1. Advance the solver by one step
2. Record the current time
3. Compute DRS angles (linear interpolation between initial and final values)
4. Retrieve Cl and Cd from the force monitor
5. Retrieve residuals (continuity, velocities, turbulence quantities)
6. Save a velocity magnitude image
7. Log progress periodically

Each iteration stores results in lists for later export.

Exports a velocity field image for each time step, which will later be combined into a video.


```
# ----- EXPORT CSV -----  
df = pd.DataFrame({  
    "Time": time_list,  
    "Cl": cl_list,  
    "Cd": cd_list,  
    "DRS1_angle": drs1_angle_list,  
    "DRS2_angle": drs2_angle_list,  
    "res_continuity": residuals_dict["continuity"],  
    "res_x-velocity": residuals_dict["x-velocity"],  
    "res_y-velocity": residuals_dict["y-velocity"],  
    "res_k": residuals_dict["k"],  
    "res_omega": residuals_dict["omega"]  
})  
  
try:  
    df.to_csv(str(csv_file), index=False)  
    logging.info(f"CSV exporté : {csv_file}")  
except Exception:  
    logging.exception("Impossible d'exporter le CSV.")
```

Saves all time-dependent data (Cl, Cd, DRS angles, residuals) into a CSV file for post-processing.

```
# ----- GENERATION MP4 (ffmpeg) -----  
def make_mp4(frames_dir: Path, output_mp4: Path, framerate: int = 25):  
    pattern = str(frames_dir / "frame_%04d.png")  
    if not any(frames_dir.glob("frame_*.png")):  
        logging.warning("Aucune frame PNG trouvée – skipping MP4 generation.")  
        return  
    # vérifier ffmpeg  
    try:  
        subprocess.run(["ffmpeg", "-version"], stdout=subprocess.DEVNULL, stderr=subprocess.DEVNULL, check=True)  
    except Exception:  
        logging.warning("ffmpeg non trouvé sur le PATH. Installez ffmpeg si vous voulez générer la vidéo.")  
        return  
    try:  
        cmd = [  
            "ffmpeg",  
            "-y",  
            "-framerate", str(framerate),  
            "-i", pattern,  
            "-c:v", "libx264",  
            "-pix_fmt", "yuv420p",  
            str(output_mp4)  
        ]  
        logging.info("Génération MP4 via ffmpeg...")  
        subprocess.run(cmd, check=True)  
        logging.info(f"Animation MP4 générée : {output_mp4}")  
    except subprocess.CalledProcessError:  
        logging.exception("ffmpeg a échoué lors de la génération de la vidéo.")  
  
make_mp4(output_dir, Path(mp4_file), framerate=25)
```


This function:

- Checks for PNG frames
- Uses ffmpeg to combine them into an MP4 video (frame_0001.png, frame_0002.png, etc.)
- Warns if ffmpeg is not installed

```
# ----- 1) Graphe des résidus vs itérations -----  
plt.figure(figsize=(10,6))  
iterations = list(range(len(residuals_dict["continuity"])))  
plt.plot(iterations, residuals_dict["continuity"], label="Continuity")  
plt.plot(iterations, residuals_dict["x-velocity"], label="X-Velocity")  
plt.plot(iterations, residuals_dict["y-velocity"], label="Y-Velocity")  
plt.plot(iterations, residuals_dict["k"], label="k")  
plt.plot(iterations, residuals_dict["omega"], label="Omega")  
plt.xlabel("Iteration")  
plt.ylabel("Residuals")  
plt.title("Résidus CFD vs Iterations (échelle linéaire)")  
plt.legend()  
plt.grid(True)  
plt.tight_layout()  
plt.savefig(project_dir / "residuals_vs_iterations.png", dpi=300)  
plt.show()  
print("Graphique des résidus sauvegardé : residuals_vs_iterations.png")
```

Plots all residuals vs iteration to visually confirm convergence.


```
# ----- 2) Graphe Cl & Cd vs DRS1 -----
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots(figsize=(10,6))
ax1.set_xlabel("Angle DRS1 (deg)")
ax1.set_ylabel("Cl", color="tab:blue")
ax1.plot(drs1_angle_list, cl_list, color="tab:blue", label="Cl")
ax1.tick_params(axis='y', labelcolor="tab:blue")
ax1.grid(True)

ax2 = ax1.twinx() # axe Y droit
ax2.set_ylabel("Cd", color="tab:red")
ax2.plot(drs1_angle_list, cd_list, color="tab:red", label="Cd")
ax2.tick_params(axis='y', labelcolor="tab:red")

fig.tight_layout()
plt.title("Cl et Cd vs Angle DRS1")
plt.savefig(project_dir / "Cl_Cd_vs_DRS1.png", dpi=300)
plt.show()
print("Graphique Cl & Cd vs DRS1 sauvegardé : Cl_Cd_vs_DRS1.png")

# ----- 3) Graphe Cl & Cd vs DRS2 -----
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots(figsize=(10,6))
ax1.set_xlabel("Angle DRS2 (deg)")
ax1.set_ylabel("Cl", color="tab:blue")
ax1.plot(drs2_angle_list, cl_list, color="tab:blue", label="Cl")
ax1.tick_params(axis='y', labelcolor="tab:blue")
ax1.grid(True)

ax2 = ax1.twinx() # axe Y droit
ax2.set_ylabel("Cd", color="tab:red")
ax2.plot(drs2_angle_list, cd_list, color="tab:red", label="Cd")
ax2.tick_params(axis='y', labelcolor="tab:red")

fig.tight_layout()
plt.title("Cl et Cd vs Angle DRS2")
plt.savefig(project_dir / "Cl_Cd_vs_DRS2.png", dpi=300)
plt.show()
print("Graphique Cl & Cd vs DRS2 sauvegardé : Cl_Cd_vs_DRS2.png")
```

Two plots show:

- Cl & Cd vs DRS1 angle
- Cl & Cd vs DRS2 angle

Each uses a dual y-axis:

- Left axis → Cl

- Right axis \rightarrow Cd

Both are saved as PNG images.

As you can see in the images, there are red waves under the fluent imported library. We still have a problem at the moment in importing this library.

The next steps will be:

- Getting the library imported
- Getting the code working
- Coding more graphics/animations (i.e. shear stress, CpT...)

4.3 More Graphics and more secure code

The most important thing in aerodynamics isn't necessarily the downforce i.e. the Cl. We must keep in mind that the front wing is working with the ground effect, so it will have a big pressure delta and a lot of shear with the flow going under the wing. This means that we have to capture a lot of different things other than the Cl and the Cd. For example, the shear stress and the total pressure coefficients CPT. We also have to capture the alpha so the angle of attack, because uh dynamic mesh is moving and having a different angle of attack at every time step.

An important thing to keep in mind is that we have to make the code very secure in terms of crashes. With the loss of researchers online it can happen that if we use the launch fluent command fluent can then crash on its own and because it is working in the background of our computer we won't even notice it. That's why we have to make a secure code in which we'll ask if fluent is launched. We will ask at each step if fluent is still open and working.


```
def start_fluent():
    print("Démarrage Fluent...")
    solver = launch_fluent(mode="solver", precision="double", processor_count=4)
    solver.file.read_case("mon_fichier.cas.h5")
    solver.setup.operators.mesh_interface.dynamic_mesh.enable()
    solver.tui.define.user_defined.compiled_functions.compile("mon_udf")
    solver.tui.define.user_defined.compiled_functions.load("mon_udf")
    return solver

# Vérifier si un fichier progress existe
def get_last_step():
    try:
        with open("progress.txt", "r") as f:
            return int(f.read().strip())
    except:
        return 0

def save_step(i):
    with open("progress.txt", "w") as f:
        f.write(str(i))

# Lancement initial Fluent
solver = start_fluent()

# On redémarre la boucle si ça crashe
while True:
    try:
        last_done = get_last_step()
        print(f"Reprise à l'itération {last_done}")

        for step in range(last_done, N_STEPS):

            #TON CODE DE CALCUL ICI
            solver.solution.run.calculation.iterate(1)

            # Extractions, images... (tout ton code normal)
            extract_velocity_contour(step)
            save_step(step)

        print("Simulation terminée sans crash.")
        break

    except Exception as e:
        print("Fluent a crashé ou ne répond plus !")
        print(traceback.format_exc())

        try:
            solver.exit()
        except:
            pass

        print("Attente 5 secondes avant redémarrage...")
        time.sleep(5)

        # Restart Fluent avec la fonction
        solver = start_fluent()

    print("Redémarrage réussi, reprise de la simulation.")
```


4.4 Connection between Fluent and Ansys

In our code, we use Python to interact with Fluence via the Python API, allowing us to control Fluent remotely. When we launch Fluent with `launch_fluent()`, it starts the Fluent solver in the background and establishes a communication link with Python. We can then use Python to load the `.cas` and `.dat`, enabling dynamic mesh compilation and loading UDFs and setting up monitors.

It also runs the transient solver step by step and extracts results such as lift, drag, residuals, and velocity fields. This way we can automate the simulation workflow without manually using different interfaces. Python acts as an automation tool for fluent sending commands and retrieving data so that we can perform post-processing, generate plots, and create animations.

The main architecture is that our script has a link with Fluent between the API PyFluent.

5. Metrics - Introduction & methods

5.1. Transient analysis

Transient analysis is separated into 2 effects:

- From the motion of the geometry
- From the pressure & velocity variation over time

5.2. Analysis Method

5.2.1. Cycle averaging Method

To limit the noise, we need to make multiple simulations, plot our desired variable, and average this variable

As we see in the figure below, as we increase the number of cycle in which we calculate the average, the curves tends to be smoother, and it is easier to distinguish particular stalls. For example, in the figure below [1], we can see that there is a bubble closure. If the signal were not smoothed, we may not have seen it.

Figure 8.— Appearance of pressure at $x/c = 0.021$ with and without conditional averaging.

5.2.2. Non dimensional parameters

Using non-dimensional variables allows us to compare different flow regimes, geometries, and motion amplitudes on an equal basis, and to identify universal trends that are independent of the specific operating conditions.

Flow regime	Geometry Frequency	Pressure	Wake Frequency	Time
$Re = \frac{\rho U_{\infty} D}{\mu}$	$k = \frac{\omega c}{2U_{\infty}}$	$C_p = \frac{p - p_{\infty}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_{\infty}^2}$	$St = \frac{fD}{U_{\infty}}$	$s = \frac{Ut}{c/2}$
		$C_{pT} = \frac{p_{tot}}{p_{dyn}}$ $= \frac{\frac{1}{2}\rho U^2 + p_s}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_{\infty}^2}$		

6. Performance Metrics - Effects of the Transient without movement of the geometry

6.1. Wake Turbulence – Turbulent kinetic Energy & Q criterion

$$Q > 0 \Rightarrow \text{Vorticity dominates}$$

$$Q < 0 \Rightarrow \text{Viscous effects dominates}$$

$$TKE = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{(u')^2} + \overline{(v')^2} + \overline{(w')^2})$$

With $\overline{(u')^2}$ the average of the squared of the oscillating component of the horizontal velocity component.

6.2. Wake Turbulence - Von Karman Streets – for Wind tunnel only

The formation of Von Karman vortex streets strongly depends on Reynolds number and angle of attack, and their shedding frequency directly governs the level of wake unsteadiness affecting downstream components.

At which Re the St is the lowest ? for different angles of attack.

Is there a significant difference between the transient and steady-state results?

At which ride height the St is the lowest ?

St vs Re for each ride height.

Identifying the conditions that minimise the Strouhal number is essential, since lower St corresponds to weaker periodic shedding and therefore a cleaner, more stable wake.

Method to calculate St :

To get the main frequency from the vertical velocity signal, we will use the FFT :

$$FFT(v_y(t))$$

After plotting our spectrum, we just have to read the frequency where the amplitude of the velocity is the highest, f_{max} .

We can now compute the Strouhal number :

$$St = \frac{f_{max}D}{U_{\infty}}$$

The frequency is dependent on the flow regime.

$$St(Re) = \frac{f_{max}(Re)D}{U_{\infty}}$$

So we need to plot St vs Re to see if there are Regimes where there is a high turbulence in the wake.

Here is an example for a cylinder :

Relationship between Strouhal number and Reynolds number for circular cylinders. Data from Lienhard (1966) and Achenbach and Heinecke (1981). $S \sim 0.21 (1 - 21/Re)$ for $40 < Re < 200$, from Roshko (1955).

Care must be taken when performing Strouhal-based analyses, as they are only meaningful when the wake remains sufficiently organized. Once the flow becomes highly chaotic, no clear periodicity can be extracted, and reliable characteristic frequencies can no longer be identified. For this reason, such an analysis is only valid in the clean, isolated-wing configuration, where the wake structure is still coherent enough to support frequency-based interpretation.

Reynolds values for a formula student car :

To know the range of Reynolds values for a formula student car, we need to know its specifications, such as :

- Mean top speed (Power limited sections)
- Mean cornering speed (Grip Limited Sections)

Based on that, we can determine both

$$Re_{max}$$

And

$$Re_{min}$$

The values of Mean top speed and Mean cornering speed are very circuit dependent. So we need to decide for which circuit the car will race.

6.3. Unsteadiness

6.3.1. Lift

This metric provides a direct quantification of the instantaneous deviation from the steady-state reference, allowing us to identify critical instants where the flow loses coherence or experiences transient separation.

$$\varepsilon_{L\%}(t) = \frac{C_L(t) - C_{L,Steady\ State}}{C_{L,Steady\ State}} * 100$$

6.3.2. Drag

Monitoring $\varepsilon_{D\%}(t)$ highlights whether the unsteady wake introduces significant drag penalties or if the fluctuations remain within acceptable operational limits.

$$\varepsilon_{D\%}(t) = \frac{C_D(t) - C_{D,Steady\ State}}{C_{D,Steady\ State}} * 100$$

7. Performance Metrics - Effects of the Transient kinematic behaviour of the geometry

7.1. Pitching Effects

7.1.1. Explanation of the problem

- Does the drag increase because of the variation of the movement of the flap?
- 2026 Rules : $\Delta t_{flap,max} = 0.4\ s$
- Plot k vs Δt_{flap}

Figure 7-1. Airfoil in DRS ON/OFF position

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 + A \sin(\omega t)$$

We can also have combined pitching and plunging, but we will first focus on each mode individually to simplify the study and to estimate the contribution of each mode.

7.1.2. Lift

At what time our lift is maximum ?

$$\omega = cte$$

(a) $k = 0.02$.

Figure 9. – Normal force and pitching moment deviations from average of all cycles.

At which reduced frequency the CL is maximum ?

Does our wing is sensitive to closing or opening ?

At which frequency the difference between the opening and closing is the highest ?

To determine the right DRS opening time : At which frequency we have a lift stall ? / or the highest lift stall ?

To answer this questions we will plot the following graphs :

$$\omega = \omega_i$$

(a) Without modification and without end plates.

Figure 30. – Lift, drag, and pitching moment as a function of α at various reduced frequencies.

7.1.3. Thrust

according to Jones [2] pitching airfoils generate thrust in specific frequencies above a certain critical value, and as a function of the pivot location. The metrics related to thrust are defined in 7.2.2.

7.1.4. Unsteadiness

Area of the Lift Vs α = Damping :

Fig. 8.5 Dynamic stall: a on set of stall, b light stall, c deep stall

Response time :

Figure 15. (top) Comparison of lift coefficient, C_L , between DNS and Indicial response for a flat plate in pitch-up maneuver at $Re = 300$. (bottom) Angle of attack vs. time. (left) Pitch-up of 8° with duration of 16 time steps. (right) Pitch-up of 16° with duration 16 time steps

7.1.5. Pitching moment

- ➔ To size the mechanism of the DRS
- ➔ We can see how much torque is applied on the axle of the DRS motor.

7.2. Heave Effects

7.2.1. Explanation of the problem

Figure 7-2. Porpoising case study

$$z(t) = z_0 + A \cos(\omega t)$$

7.2.2. Thrust efficiency

according to Jones [2] plunging airfoils generate thrust over the whole frequency range.

We know that

$$\eta_t = \frac{C_{thrust}}{C_{power}}$$

With

$$C_{power} = -\bar{C}_L \dot{z} - \bar{C}_m \dot{\alpha}$$

And

$$C_{thrust} = \frac{T}{\frac{1}{2} \rho U_\infty^2 c}$$

Jones [2] has tested many cases :

here is the plot of η_t vs k for each configuration :

We can see that the maximum thrust efficiency is produced at the lowest reduced frequency for a single airfoil. For the other configurations, we can see that the thrust efficiency has a maximum.

The cases in Fig 13b and 13c does not corresponds very well to our case. But from this study, we learned that if there is something behind the wing, a maximum should exists. And in our case, there is the tyre behind the wing : so maybe, a peak value exists. We need to test with simple geometries : (flap with cylinder behind)

We now understand that we need to know at each heave reduced frequency the wing has the highest η_t .

7.2.3. Lift or Drag vs frequency

This metric will help us to answer to the following question :

Is there a critical frequency that we must not exceed ? where the lift drops ?

8. Validation of our results

8.1. Sinusoidal input (heave or pitching)

From [3] we know that :

$$\underline{C_L} = \frac{2\pi}{U} \underline{C}(k) \left(\dot{h} + \frac{\dot{\alpha}b}{2} + U\alpha \right) - \frac{\pi b}{2U^2} \left(\frac{b\ddot{\alpha}}{4} + U\dot{\alpha} \right)$$

With

$$b = \frac{c}{2}$$

$$\underline{C}(k) = \frac{H_1^{(2)}(k)}{H_1^{(2)}(k) + iH_0^{(2)}(k)}$$

$$C_L = \Re(\underline{C}_L)$$

So finally, we have in pitching condition :

We can use this curve to validate our results.

8.1.1. Ramp input

According to Ülgün [3], the analytical formula for the lift coefficient is given by :

$$C_L(s) = \frac{\pi b}{U^2} (\ddot{h} + U\dot{\alpha}) - \frac{2\pi}{U} \left[w\left(\frac{b}{2}, s\right) + (w * \dot{\varphi})(s) \right]$$

With

$$w\left(\frac{b}{2}, s\right) = \dot{h} + \frac{\dot{\alpha}b}{2} + U\alpha$$

So with a ramp pitching angle :

we should have the following response :

9. Meshing metrics

These metrics will be used to know how much precision do we need on each part of the geometry.

9.1. Ansys Fluent Meshing parameters

Longitudinal Mesh gradient = longitudinal Growth rate

Vertical Mesh gradient rate = Vertical Growth rate

9.2. Near wall mesh

To size our cells, we need to know how much change there is on each part of the geometry. For a given 2D geometry, we can define 2 essential metrics :

$$\frac{\partial V_n(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \Big|_{y=0}$$

And

$$\frac{\partial V_t(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{y=0}$$

With V_t and V_n the tangential & vertical velocity components. We can normalize these quantities with respect to the chord and to the freestream velocity to get non dimensional numbers, that we will call A and B .

$$A = \frac{\partial V_n(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{c}{U_\infty}$$

$$B = \frac{\partial V_t(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{c}{U_\infty}$$

9.3. Wake mesh

Turbulence scale $k - \omega$ SST

The $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model switches between $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \omega$, in the following way :

$k - \varepsilon$ for a slip wall / wake

$k - \omega$ for a no slip wall

So to determine the turbulence length scale in the wake, we need to use a $k - \varepsilon$ metric :

According to Wilcox, we have :

$$L_T = C_\mu * \frac{k^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\varepsilon}$$

10. Summary

	Porpoising effects	DRS ON/OFF effects (with a step angle)	Fixed Geometry
FW Performance	$C_L(t)$ vs k	$C_L(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$\varepsilon_{L\%}(t)$ vs Re
	$C_D(t)$ vs k	$C_D(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$\varepsilon_{D\%}(t)$ vs Re
	(C_L/C_D) vs k	$(C_L/C_D)(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$(C_L/C_D)(t)$ vs Re
	$\eta_t(t)$ vs k	$\eta_t(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$\eta_t(t)$ vs Re
Wake turbulence	$TKE(t)$ vs k	$TKE(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$TKE(t)$ vs Re
	$Q(t)$ vs k	$Q(t)$ vs $\dot{\alpha}/\dot{\alpha}_{min}$	$Q(t)$ vs Re
			St vs Re
Transient effects quantification	Phase lag	Phase lag	
	C_L vs α Area	C_L vs α Area	
	Response time	Response time	

Bibliography

- [1] NASA, “Dynamic Stall Experiment on the NACA 0012 Airfoil,” *Technical Paper*.
- [2] P. M. Jones KD, “An Experimental and Numerical Investigation of Flapping-Wing Propulsion,” 1999.
- [3] Fundamentals of Modern Unsteady Aerodynamics.